

Grant Agreement No: 101004761

AIDAinnova

Advancement and Innovation for Detectors at Accelerators
Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures project AIDAINNOVA

DELIVERABLE REPORT

CHARACTERISATION OF SMALL SIZE MRPC PROTOTYPES FOR FAST TIMING AND HIGH RATES

DELIVERABLE: D7.1

Document identifier:	AIDAinnova-D7.2
Due date of deliverable:	March 2024
Report release date:	26/04/2024
Work package:	WP7: Gaseous Detectors
Lead beneficiary:	INFN Bologna
Document status:	Final

Abstract:

The Multigap Resistive Plate Chamber (MRPC) is a gaseous detector that can offer excellent time performance and its cost to cover large areas is low. Most RPC-type detectors are currently using $C_2F_4H_2$ -based gas mixtures that have very high Global Warming Potential (GWP). Another interesting feature of MRPCs is the high-rate capability. We built a double-stack MRPC using low-resistive glass with a bulk resistivity of $10^9 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$ and tested it at the T10 beam facility at CERN. We also tested it with both the standard and a more ecological gas mixture.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2024

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The Advancement and Innovation for Detectors at Accelerators (AIDAinnova) project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 101004761. AIDAinnova began in April 2021 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	Y.W.Baek J.S. Kim	GWNU GWNU	04/03/2024
Edited by	Y.W.Baek J.S. Kim D.W. Kim M.C.S. Williams D. Hatzifotiadou	GWNU GWNU SNU INFN INFN	13/03/2024
Reviewed by	S. Dalla Tore B. Schmidt	INFN CERN	30/03/2024
Approved by	P. Giacomelli	INFN	26/04/2024

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Executive summary

With the MRPC detector technology, it is easy to cover a large active area at a low cost; it also provides excellent timing resolution that can be used to identify particles. However, future collider experiments require higher rate performance and the use of more ecological gases. We built a small double stack MRPC that was manufactured using low resistivity glass that has a bulk resistivity of the order of $10^9 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$. The MRPC has 10 gas gaps of $235 \mu\text{m}$ width; the glass thickness was 0.5 mm. It has a strip-type readout with electrodes of 19 cm in length. To measure the performance, we installed the low-resistive MRPC and an equivalent normal glass MRPC, built with normal 'soda-lime' glass ($10^{12} \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$.) in the T10 beam facility to compare their performances. For the test, the standard gas and an ecological gas have been used. The MRPC reached an efficiency of 98% and a time resolution of around 70 ps for the two gas mixtures at a low particle rate. In the case of the low-resistivity glass MRPC, there was no degradation of performance up to the highest value of 63 kHz/cm^2 .

1. INTRODUCTION

In high-energy physics experiments, the Multigap Resistive Plate Chamber (MRPC) [1] provides an excellent timing measurement for charged particles. Furthermore, we can make a large detection area thanks to the low cost and its ease of construction. Thanks to its timing property, the MRPC could be used as a Time-of-Flight (TOF) detector in high-energy physics and nuclear physics experiments, such as ALICE [2], HADES [3], and STAR [4] experiments. A MRPC detector built with standard 'soda lime' float glass with a bulk resistivity of $\sim 10^{12} \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$ operates well below $1 \text{ kHz}/\text{cm}^2$ of particle flux. A possible and known idea to improve the rate capability of MRPC is to use low resistive glass that can help to quickly rebuild the electric field inside the gas gaps. Concerning the MRPCs at high rate, the Compressed Baryonic Matter (CBM) at the Facility for Antiproton and Ion Research (FAIR) [5] will equip the TOF detector that can reach $25 \text{ kHz}/\text{cm}^2$ [6]. A previous study on the performance of MRPC exposed to beams focused on a small area at rates up to $30 \text{ kHz}/\text{cm}^2$ was reported in [7]. Further studies have been done in [8,9], using low resistivity glass of the order of $10^9 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$; an efficiency of 95% has been achieved with a continuous flux of $200 \text{ kHz}/\text{cm}^2$. All these tests have been done using the standard gas mixture based on 98% of R134a ($\text{C}_2\text{F}_4\text{H}_2$) and 2% of SF_6 to operate the MRPCs. These two gases have very high Global Warming Potential (GWP) values, around 1,430 for R134a and 23,000 for SF_6 , leading to a GWP for the mixture of about 2040. After some studies [10,11] to find an ecological substitute for these greenhouse gases, the HFO-1234ze ($\text{C}_3\text{F}_4\text{H}_2$) is suggested to be the most promising candidate. It has a GWP of only 6. This report provides the beam test result carried out at T10 with a small MRPC which was built by using low-resistive glass.

2. SMALL MRPCS

We tested two MRPCs with different designs.

- One MRPC with soda-lime float glass, with bulk resistivity of $\sim 10^{12} \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$,
 - hereafter referred to as HRG (High Resistive Glass) chamber,
 - consisting of 2 stacks with 4 gaps each,
 - with a gap size of $250 \mu\text{m}$, made by using a nylon fishing line,
 - using $400 \mu\text{m}$ thick soda-lime float glass,
 - $19 \times 19 \text{ cm}^2$ of active area, painted to have a resistance of $\sim 2 \text{ M}\Omega/\text{square}$,
 - readout strips of 7 mm width and 1 mm between the strips.
- Another MRPC with low resistive glass, with bulk resistivity $\sim 10^9 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$,
 - hereafter referred to as LRG (Low Resistive Glass) chamber,
 - consisting of 2 stacks of 5 gaps each,
 - with a gap size of $235 \mu\text{m}$ made by a ceramic fishing line,
 - using $500 \mu\text{m}$ thick low resistive glass,
 - $18 \times 18 \text{ cm}^2$ of active area, painted to have a resistance of about $2 \text{ M}\Omega/\text{square}$,
 - readout strip with 7 mm wide and 1 mm interval between strips.

The cross-section of the MRPC with low-resistive glasses is shown in Figure 1. The MRPC with soda-lime float glasses has the same structure but the glass thickness, fishing line diameter, and the number of gaps are different.

Figure 1: Schematic cross-section view of 10-gas MRPC

The differential signal per channel formed by the cathode strip and the anode strip are amplified and discriminated by NINO ASICs [12]. The threshold of NINOs was set to 40 fC and the LVDS outputs from the NINOs are sent to the CAEN V1290TDC which provides 25 ps LSB.

3. SETUP AT TEST BEAM

The beam test was carried out at the T10 beam line at the PS at CERN. Two scintillators for the trigger, P1 and P2, were positioned before and after MRPCs. The active area size of these scintillators was about 10 x 10 cm². At the very front, two scintillator bars (S1, S2, S3, S4) provided an accurate time reference T0 in terms of the average time of these scintillators. However, during the beam test, the Constant Fraction Discriminator (CFD) unit malfunctioned, therefore the time resolution of these 4 timing scintillators was estimated to be 130 ps. As the timing precision of an MRPC is better than 100 ps, this time reference could only be used for qualitative comparisons, rather than quantitative estimations. The described beam test setup is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematics of the experimental setup at T10

4. EFFICIENCY

The chamber efficiency is defined as a ratio between the number of events that give a hit in at least 1 strip and the total number of triggered events. The measured efficiencies and the cluster sizes for two different gases for both MRPCs are shown in Figure 3 as a function of the electric field strength in the gas gaps. Here, the cluster size means the average number of fired strips per event.

Figure 3: Efficiency curves and cluster size for two different gases on two MRPCs, LRG and HRG.

Figure 4: Measured dark currents and 75 percentiles of the TOT distributions versus electric field at a beam intensity of $500 \sim 700 \text{ Hz/cm}^2$.

When using the standard gas mixture, the efficiency plateau is shown to start at about 10 kV/mm for both chambers, corresponding to the applied voltage of 10 kV for the HRG chamber and 11.75 kV for the LRG chamber. The efficiency of both chambers reaches 98%. With the ecological gas, the efficiency plateau is reached at electric fields of 13 kV/mm, corresponding to high voltages of 13 kV and 15.3 kV for HRG and LRG chambers, respectively. The maximum efficiencies of HRG and LRG chambers reach 95% and 98%, respectively. The reduction in efficiency of the HRG chamber is caused by a strip with a slightly lower efficiency of 92%, because of the low exposure to the beam. Excluding this strip, the efficiency of the HRG chamber reaches 97%. It is shown that the average cluster size of the LRG chamber increases exponentially as opposed to that of the HRG chamber, above the value of the electric field required to reach the efficiency plateau, indicating streamer generation.

The measured dark current and the 75 percentile of the Time Over Threshold (TOT) distribution are shown in Figure 4 as a function of the electric field. At the start of the efficiency plateau, the dark currents are lower than $1.0 \mu\text{A}$ in all cases. However, when both types of gases used reach the efficiency plateau, the current in the LRG chamber increases significantly faster than the HRG chamber, thus limiting the maximum operating voltage. Unlike HRG chambers, where the increase is much more suppressed, the presence of streamers in LRG increases dramatically once they reach the efficiency plateau. Particularly in high-rate counting experiments, increasing the streamer rate would accelerate the detector aging, which is a major concern when using low-resistivity glasses.

5. TIME MEASUREMENT

Figure 5: Distribution of measured signal TOT versus operating voltages for HRG chamber using standard gas (top left), HRG chamber using ecological gas (top right), LRG chamber using standard gas (bottom left), and LRG chamber using ecological gas (bottom right)

The time measured on all strips in each chamber is individually calibrated to obtain the most precise time measurement that can be achieved with the chamber. The calibration procedure consists of time slewing correction and offset correction for each strip. For each event triggered in each chamber, only the strip that produced the signal corresponding to the largest TOT is considered. The strip TOT is defined as the average value for the two ends of the strip. Figure 5 shows the distribution of signal TOT for different operating

voltages. For the LRG chamber, the TOT measurement is affected by signal reflection at operating voltages above 10.5 kV for the standard gas and 14.5 kV for the ecological gas. The TOT distribution displays one, two, or three local maxima. These correspond to a signal with no reflection, a signal with reflection on one side, and a signal with reflection visible on both sides of the strip, respectively. It is shown that as the operating voltage increases, the magnitude of the signal increases, increasing the probability that reflection will occur, and equally decreasing the probability that reflection will not occur. No reflections are visible in the HRG chamber. Indeed, we use 50 Ω impedance matchers in the chamber based on the HRT chamber. We assumed that this value would not change much on the LRG chamber.

For the ecological gas, the TOT distribution for both LRG and HRG chambers shows large tails, highlighting the increased presence of streamers that were difficult to observe in Figure 4. To minimize the influence of position along the strip the average of the signal times at both ends of the strip is used as the particle arrival time. The time slewing correction using a fourth-order polynomial applied to each strip is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Left: signal leading time difference versus signal TOT for the strip of the LRG chamber. Also, shown in red is the fourth-order polynomial fitting function. Right: signal leading time difference versus signal TOT after correction

Due to the channel-by-channel variation of the electronics including the layout of the printed circuit board and different NINO chips, the mean values of the arrival time vary from strip to strip as shown in Figure 7. An offset is therefore applied for each strip to equalize their response times.

Figure 7: Normalized distribution of individual strip time differences to T_0 before correction (left) and after applying correction (right) for the LRG chamber. The plain black histograms represent the combined measurement using all the strips.

Figure 8: Normalized distribution of the time differences between the LRG and the HRG chamber using standard gas (left) and ecological gas (right)

The time differences measured between the LRG and the HRG chambers for both types of gas are shown in Figure 8. For the standard gas, the sigma of this difference is 100 ps, which gives an average chamber time resolution of $100/\sqrt{2} = 71$ ps. For the ecological gas, the sigma is 107 ps, and assuming equal contributions from both chambers, the average chamber resolution is $107/\sqrt{2} = 76$ ps.

6. RATE CAPABILITY

The setup was then exposed to particle beams with stepwise increasing intensity ranging from 2.5 kHz/cm² to 28 kHz/cm² for the standard gas and 2.5 kHz/cm² to 63 kHz/cm² for the ecological gas. The event rate is estimated as the number of S1, S2, S3, and S4 coincidences divided by the duration of the spill time (~400 ms) and the triggering area (4 cm²) of the (S1-S4) scintillators. It is also technically possible to use recorded event times to estimate the instantaneous particle rate during the time of the spill. However, this method is not sufficiently accurate due to the large dead time of the acquisition system, especially at high rates. A profile of the estimated particle fraction as a function of the spill time is shown in Figure 9.

The measured efficiencies for two types of gases and various beam intensities are shown in Figure 10. As expected, the efficiency of the HRG chamber gradually decreases as the rate increases. On the other hand, the efficiency curve of the LRG chamber remains unchanged up to 28 kHz/cm² for the standard gas and up to 63 kHz/cm² for the ecological gas.

The variation of efficiency with the spill time is shown in Figure 11. As charge accumulates on the surface of the glasses, the electric field in the gas gap decreases and the efficiency gradually decreases as a function of the time during the spill. The fact that the measured efficiencies are still decreasing even at the end of the spill from the HRG chamber indicates that a longer particle spill of equivalent rate would have led to reduced overall efficiencies compared to the results we obtained. This may explain why the measured efficiency of the HRG chamber is surprisingly high even at rates up to 6 kHz/cm². It is also worth mentioning that the irradiation area is limited, which greatly reduces the impact of high particle rates. No significant variation in efficiency during the spill has been observed with the LRG chamber.

Figure 9: Estimated particle rate as a function of the time in spill for a run taken at the highest beam intensity.

Figure 10: Measured chamber efficiencies versus electric field for the two gas types and the different particle fluxes.

Figure 11: Measured efficiencies versus time in particle spill for different particle fluxes and using the ecological gas. The operating voltage is 16 kV. Left: HRG chamber. Right: LRG chamber

The measured time resolution as a function of beam intensity for two types of gases and different operating voltages is shown in Figure 12. The time measurement capability of the LRG chamber appears to be unaffected by the rate increases because the change in time resolution with respect to T0 is contained within the statistical error. Thus, in the case of the standard gas, the increase in the time resolution of the difference between the LRG and the HRG chamber is entirely due to the decreasing performance of the HRG chamber. We observed that the increase in time resolution between the LRG and HRG chambers using the ecological gas is negligible up to the particle rate of 63 kHz/cm^2 .

Figure 12: Measured resolution of the time difference versus beam intensity for different operating voltages. Top row: standard gas, bottom row: ecological gas. Left column: time difference between LRG chamber and HRG chamber, middle column: time difference between LRG chamber and T0 detector, Right column: time difference between HRG chamber and T0 detector.

Figure 13 shows the normalized distribution of time differences for several different time intervals of the spill. Using the standard gas the time resolution of the HRG chamber deteriorates with the spill duration. However, with the ecological gas, the time resolution of HRG appears to be much less affected by the spill time.

Figure 13: Normalized distribution of the time differences for different time intervals during the spill. Top row: standard gas, beam intensity 28 kHz/cm². Bottom row: ecological gas, beam intensity 49 kHz/cm². Left column: time difference between LRG chamber and HRG chamber, middle column: time difference between LRG chamber and T0 detector, right column: time difference between HRG chamber and T0 detector.

7. CONCLUSION AND PLAN

The performance of a low-resistivity glass double-stack MRPC with 10 gaps and 235 μm spacing was evaluated at particle rates up to 28 kHz/cm² using a mixture of 98% R134a (C₂F₄H₂) and 2% of SF₆, and up to 63 kHz/cm² using a pure ecological gas HFO-1234ze (C₃F₄H₂). The efficiency of this chamber, measured with a beam spot area of 4 cm², reaches 98% for both gas types. The time resolution is estimated to be about 70 ps. No performance degradation was observed up to a maximum rate of 63 kHz/cm². The use of low-resistivity glass MRPC and ecological gas may be a promising solution for use in high-counting rate experiments. To confirm that statement, the LRG chamber must be exposed to a high particle rate over the entire active area. In addition, an increase in streamers was observed when using low-resistivity glasses compared to the standard glass and when using ecological gas. This raises concerns about the aging of this detector when operating in high-rate experiments. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the aging of the low-resistive glass MRPC as a first step, followed by the MRPC aging using an ecological gas mixture.

As next step, we plan a new design of the MRPC detector, using LRG glass. This will read data two-dimensionally with a single stack. The beam test is planned to measure the rate capability at the highest possible beam rate while making the beam as wide as possible.

8. REFERENCES

- [1] E. Cerron Zeballos, et al., A new type of resistive plate chamber: The multigap RPC, Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment 374 (1996) 132–135.
- [2] A. Akindinov, al., Latest results on the performance of the multigap resistive plate chamber used for the ALICE TOF, Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment 533 (2004) 74–78. Proceedings of the Seventh International Workshop on Resistive Plate Chambers and Related Detectors.
- [3] D. Belver, et al., The HADES RPC inner TOF wall, Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment 602 (2009) 687–690. Proceedings of the 9th International Workshop on Resistive Plate Chambers and Related Detectors.
- [4] B. Bonner, et al., A multigap resistive plate chamber prototype for time-of-flight for the STAR experiment at RHIC, Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment 478 (2002) 176–179. Proceedings of the ninth Int.Conf. on Instrumentation.
- [5] Ablyazimov, T. et al., Challenges in QCD matter physics –The scientific programme of the Compressed Baryonic Matter experiment at FAIR, Eur. Phys. J. A 53 (2017) 60.
- [6] I. Deppner et al., The CBM Time-of-Flight wall — a conceptual design, Journal of Instrumentation 9 (2014) C10014.
- [7] Z. Liu, et al., 20 gas gaps Multigap Resistive Plate Chamber: Improved rate capability with excellent time resolution, Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment 908 (2018) 383– 387.
- [8] Z. Liu, et al., A Multigap Resistive Plate Chamber built with thin low-resistive glass: High rate capability with excellent time resolution, Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment 928 (2019) 7–12.
- [9] Z. Liu, et al., Novel low resistivity glass: MRPC detectors for ultra high rate applications, Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment 959 (2020) 163483.
- [10] L. Benussi, et al., A study of HFO-1234ze (1,3,3,3- Tetrafluoropropene) as an eco-friendly replacement in RPC detectors, 2015. [arXiv:1505.01648](https://arxiv.org/abs/1505.01648).
- [11] M. Abbrescia, et al., Eco-friendly gas mixtures for Resistive Plate Chambers based on tetrafluoropropene and Helium, Journal of Instrumentation 11 (2016) P08019.
- [12] F. Anghinolfi, et al., NINO: an ultra-fast and low-power front-end amplifier/discriminator ASIC designed for the multigap resistive plate chamber, Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment 533 (2004) 183–187. Proceedings of the Seventh International Workshop on Resistive Plate Chambers and Related Detectors.